

DISTINCTIVE FEATURES OF PROTECTING YOUNG PEOPLE FROM MANIPULATIVE INFLUENCES

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Annotation: in this article, an understanding of manipulation is given to young people and a brief tariff on the peculiarities of protection against manipulation that affects young people in our country.

Keywords: What is manipulation, differentiation of manipulation, monopoly, Stress, emotion, behavior, independence, self-control

The main part: manipulation is a hidden psychological effect directed at people, forcing them to act in accordance with the goals of the manipulator. Each person is capable of manipulative behavior to varying degrees, but some people are more prone to this and achieve more success than others.

Here we begin by determining the position of manipulation in the structure of the negotiation process. Strategy, tactics and style are the main elements that characterize negotiations. Various authors of the negotiation process-researchers - psychologists, diplomats, social scientists have studied different ways of understanding and differentiating the concepts of strategy, tactics and communication style .

Manipulation is different from General influence and persuasion . Non-manipulative exposure is generally considered harmless and is not seen as excessive coercion of an individual's right to accept or reject exposure. Persuasion is the ability to move others to the desired action, usually within a certain goal. Persuasion often attempts to influence people's beliefs, religion, motives, or behavior. Influence and persuasion, in contrast to manipulation, are neither positive nor negative.

Manipulation bypasses conscious control and affects us from within, like our desire or decision. It is an effect that a person does not perceive or identify as an effect; it is an effect that a person begins to perceive other people's intentions as his own. Simply put, manipulation is a latent effect. However, not all forms of human interaction can be attributed to one or another point. Therefore, E.L.Dotsenko distinguished five types of interaction response.

Dominance. It is characterized by:

- ✓ attitude towards the partner as something that is not taken into account by the interest of the person or as a means of achieving goals;
- ✓ the desire to possess, dispose of, have an unlimited one-sided advantage;
- ✓ simplified, one-sided perception of a partner, the presence of stereotypical ideas about him;
- ✓ the existence of an open imperative effect

Manipulation. It is characterized by:

- attitude to a partner as a " kind of thing of a kind
- the desire to have a one-sided advantage, combined with the eye, to the impression made;
- the presence of a latent effect with indirect pressure, not direct.

Competition. It is characterized by:

- ❖ the attitude towards the partner of the clock as a dangerous and unpredictable object;
- ❖ the desire to surpass him, to " fight " a one-sided advantage;
- ❖ use of both hidden and open influence (some types of "subtle" manipulation, tactical agreements)

Cooperation. It is characterized by:

- ✚ equal attitude to the partner;
- ✚ the desire not to harm oneself without violating the interests of other people;
- ✚ the use of methods of interaction, not influence (agreement).

Commonwealth. It is characterized by:

- ✓ attitude towards the partner as a valuable person;
- ✓ seeking to unite, joint activities to achieve similar or appropriate goals;
- ✓ the use of consent (consensus) as the primary mode of interaction

Manipulation is a behavioral strategy, but it usually manifests itself as a tactic in negotiations.

Once the negotiation strategy is identified, there is a need to develop tactics to manage them. A tactic is a technique, method, process, or set of interrelated methods to implement a chosen strategy. The goal of the strategy is to determine what needs to be achieved in negotiations, while the task of tactics is to determine exactly how to work in coordination with strategic intentions. Manipulation, as one of the many tactics present in the arsenal of negotiators' behavior, is a common method of achieving a goal.

Conclusion: the more prone a person is to manipulation, the higher the level of anxiety. Manipulators are domineering, aggressive and arrogant. They are characterized by the presence of internal contradictions. If they are challenged and experience a conflict between the desire to achieve the goal and the lack of resources to do so, they are concerned.

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